

Response of coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) to low concentrations of NaCl

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Coriander (*Coriandrum sativum*L.) is rich in essential oils, proteins, vitamin C and organic acids. It is widely used spice plant, but it is also well known for its medicinal features. In that sense, the whole plant of coriander is effective, and the experts claim that coriander is a good antioxidant, antiseptic, antispasmodic, diuretic and aphrodisiac. Because salinity may change biochemical properties of plant tissues, the aim of this experiment was to explore the effect of low concentration of NaCl (which can often be found in irrigation waters) on biomass production and some biochemical parameters.

The seeds of coriander (obtained from the collection of the Institute of Field and Vegetable crops in Novi Sad) were sown in shallow, round dishes filled with previously sterilized sand and watered with deionized water. After germination, plants were transferred to pots containing ½ strength Hoagland solution. After 14 days, different amounts of NaCl were added into nutrient solution (0-control, 0.2, 0.6 or 1.2 g NaCl/l). There were 7 replications of each treatment, with 8 plants per replication. Analyses were done 21 days after the beginning of the treatment. Biomass production (of leaves, stems and roots separately), concentrations of vitamin C, free proline and MDA (as a measure of lipid peroxidation) were measured.

Leaf biomass statistically significantly differed between treatments. Increasing salt concentration induced increase in the content of vitamin C. Addition of 0.6 and 1.2 g NaCl/l led to an increase in the content of vitamin C about 25%. The concentration of free proline increased significantly only at a concentration of 1.2 g NaCl/l. Similarly to the content of vitamin C, the highest concentrations of the salts significantly changed amount of MDA compared to the control, suggesting that even relatively low concentrations of NaCl provoke significant changes in coriander herb.